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TRAINING STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES OF RUSSIA: MAIN TASKS AND FORECASTS FOR THE FUTURE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the physical culture and sports activities of young students at the stage of vocational training at a university, where physical culture acquires professional importance, since it contributes to the development of a young organism, the formation of healthy lifestyle skills, which in turn leads to the improvement of the culture of physical activity and provides psychophysical preparation for future professional activity.

Keywords: sport, university, country, education, student.

I. INTRODUCTION

The need to popularize physical culture and sports among students is due not only to the needs and individual rights of young people, but also to the age characteristics of their development, constantly changing living conditions, as well as the "social order" of society for the training of highly qualified specialists. These provisions are reflected in the Federal Law "On Physical Culture and Sports in the Russian Federation".

On the basis of this law, taking into account other fundamental legislative, instructive and program documents that determine the main focus, volume and content of physical education classes in higher education, an exemplary program for the discipline "Physical Culture" was drawn up. In accordance with this program, the goal of physical education of university students is the formation of physical culture of the individual and the ability to use various means of physical culture, sports and tourism for the preservation and promotion of health, psychophysical training and self-training for future professional activities. The contradiction is determined by the demands of social practice in increasing the physical readiness of university graduates for effective production activities, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, by the lack of motivational and value orientations of students in the field of physical culture and sports.

II. METHODOLOGY

One of the leading principles of the state educational policy is the humanistic orientation of education, which determines the priority of universal values, the creation of conditions for the comprehensive development of the individual based on a student-centered approach. This approach allows creating conditions for students that would contribute to the process of self-realization, creative activity and personal growth. It determines the need to improve the content of physical education classes at the university, to increase their educational and health-improving efficiency. The methodological basis of the study is modern scientific ideas of the psychological theory of activity (P.Ya. Galperin, A.N. Leontiev), the concept of personality-oriented education by V.V. Serikov, the main scientific provisions of the theory of education in the field of physical culture (V.K. Balsevich, M.Ya. Vilensky, L.I. Lubysheva, L.P. Matveev, G.G. Natalov, Yu.M. Nikolaev, A.V. Lotonenko), the theory of sports (V.N. Platonov, S.M. Vaitsekhovskiy, Yu.V. Verkhoshansky, Yu.V. Menkhin), the theory and methods of wrestling (V.M. Igumenov, G.S. Tumanyan, B. A. Podlivaev, R.A. Piloyan, B.I. Tarakanov, V.I. Grigoriev).

III. RESULTS

As a rule, physical culture is associated only with the improvement of the natural basis of a person, his physical organization. At the same time, being one of the human and social values, it acts as a culture of the way of life of people, it is a prerequisite for other levels of general cultural being - a culture of worldview, political, moral, ethical and aesthetic. In physical culture, a person strives for harmonization with himself, the world around him, nature and society. The fact that 25% of cadets, 32% of university students have little interest in physical culture and sports events indicates the insufficiency of educational work on the formation of physical culture of the individual and the lack of value orientations for a healthy lifestyle among young students.

They receive the vast majority of information about the importance of physical culture and sports activity from mass media sources - newspapers, television, posters, etc., i.e. passive means of physical education. Many believe that it is necessary to get acquainted with sports in practice - in competitive and training activities. At the same time, both senior schoolchildren and students extremely rarely take part in competitions of various sizes, excluding athletes. The nature of work in compulsory physical education classes is determined by those means and methods that purposefully develop the necessary physical qualities and motor skills.

We believe that a significant factor that has a beneficial effect on the development of the individual is the planning of physical education classes in such a way that individually attractive forms of physical activity act as a reinforcing basis for developing the need for systematic physical exercises, i.e. the planning of the educational-training process should be carried out in such a way that the level of fitness was achieved, first of all, due to the forms of physical activity that are attractive to each individual.

The organization of physical culture and sports activities, taking into account the interests of the individual and his physical capabilities, largely determines the emergence of personality skills in adolescence: the discovery of one's inner world, the formation of a more or less stable image of the "I" associated with the development of self-consciousness and the emergence of a special attitude to one's personality.

Without the formation of a personal "picture of the world" with all the complex of consciousness and self-consciousness that generates it, it is impossible to ensure "neither the development of scientific theoretical thinking, nor the ability to learn in the world of scientific knowledge."

Therefore, the use of the results of one's own motor experience in the process of physical education greatly contributes to the formation and development of cognitive interests and personality activity.

Conceptual framework illustrating relationships among physical activity, physical fitness, health, and academic performance.

Therefore, physical education, providing a combination of knowledge; productive existence (sports and recreation activities); human values (emotions); world of culture (cultural symbols and signs), contributes to the "expansion of consciousness" of a young person.

At present, the share of physical labor in production and at home has sharply decreased, and in the future this trend will increase even more. At the same time, the impact on the body of adverse environmental factors is significantly increased, especially in industrial cities, which negatively affects people's health. The current century is characterized by an increased flow of information. Moreover, the information whirlwind is intensifying, and this is a powerful load on the sense organs, on those very nerve cells that do not differ in great stability and endurance. Therefore, now the question of the prevention of various diseases has arisen not only with the help of medical methods, but also with the help of physical exercises.

Just as it is impossible to develop aesthetic needs without visiting theaters, museums, exhibitions, it is also impossible to develop physical culture and sports needs without engaging in physical improvement. To prevent this from happening, it is necessary to increase the scientifically based amount of classes from 2-3 per week (this is only 11% of the necessary physical activity) up to 6-12 hours with theoretical and practical training, which is necessary for the normal development of the body.

If the muscles are inactive and their nutrition worsens, then the volume and strength decrease, elasticity and elasticity decrease: they become weak, flabby while the activity of internal organs deteriorates. Therefore, restriction in movements and a passive lifestyle lead to various pathological changes in organs and tissues.

One of the general recommendations that is suitable for people of all ages: if you want to be strong and hardy - get tired! This advice is correct, and you can achieve high performance only if you systematically tire yourself with physical activity.

As a result of systematic stimulation of recovery processes, structural changes also occur that increase the potential of the body. There is an accelerated recovery of tissues damaged in the process of intense activity, wound healing is enhanced. Thanks to this, a person becomes better protected from the adverse effects of environmental factors. The reasons for underestimating the role of physical culture are not so much objective as subjective. These include a lulling feeling of well-being and physical health, since the consequences of physical inactivity and other risk factors do not appear immediately, but are distant at considerable intervals of time. A person in his mind with difficulty connects these phenomena.

A socio-ecological systems (SEC) model highlighting the multifaceted influences and interactions of Higher Education experiences, livelihood, and lifestyle on an individual’s health and wellbeing during a global pandemic phenomenon.

Studies conducted among bedridden people and astronauts who were in a state of weightlessness have shown that people quickly lose bone mass if they are unable to overcome their own weight. On the other hand, a study of the hands of tennis players showed that the bone tissue of the leading hand is denser than the bone tissue of the other, since the leading one experiences great physical exertion. According to numerous studies conducted in various groups, including women with osteoporosis and people in nursing homes, exercise not only prevents bone loss, but can even increase bone density (with enough calcium in the diet).

Core elements of physical literacy.

Osteoporosis is not an inevitable consequence of aging for those who take care of their physical activity. But you need to do this in accordance with your age and state of health.

At the age of 20-40, the goal of physical education is to lay the foundation for a long and active life. At this age, walks, various sports, outdoor games are required.

At the age of 40-60 years, the goal is to minimize bone loss, especially the refusal to use the elevator, transport, the intensity of sports in the absence of serious medical contraindications.

At the age of over 60 years, the goal is to reduce the risk of falls and the possibility of fractures, especially for fragile women. It is necessary to choose a program of physical exercises according to age and level of fitness, walking is required.

Patients with osteoporosis, goal: reduce the risk of falls and the possibility of fractures, increase bone mass. The thinned bones of patients require a number of restrictions in the exercise program. You will need to consult a specialist in physical education and a physiotherapist, but in any case, walking for 30 minutes 5-7 times a week is indicated.

IV. CONCLUSION

Long-term studies conducted by the departments of physical culture of various universities of the country indicate that the state of health of student youth causes serious concern. The number of students involved in special medical groups is increasing from year to year and in many of them is up to 30% of the total number of students. It should be emphasized that the State Committee for Sports developed in 2021 the Federal Target Program "Physical Education and Improvement of Children, Adolescents and Youth in the Russian Federation".

Of great interest in this Program are data that show that underestimation of the role of physical culture and sports in a healthy lifestyle leads to significant state losses. Thus, the state costs for the treatment of sick children, adolescents and youth per year is about 40 billion rubles, incl. for the payment of benefits to parents - 10.5 billion rubles.

If, through active physical culture and sports, it is possible to actually reduce the number of sick children and young people by 10% (and according to experts, this figure is quite real and can reach 50% or more), then the state can receive real prevented economic damage, in the amount of almost 4 billion rubles. Experts also calculated that the funds allocated for recreational activities are 26 times less than the funds that are currently spent on the treatment and rehabilitation of patients.

The next direction in the development of physical culture and sports in Russian universities should be the improvement (reconstruction and construction) of the material and technical base in Voronezh universities - stadiums, sports palaces, swimming pools, sports and gyms, etc.

And, finally, the main directions should include further improvement of the legal and regulatory framework for the development of physical culture and sports in the region, incl. and among student youth. Some experts believe that it is the development and improvement of the legislative framework in the field of physical culture and sports that is the main direction in the implementation of state policy in the development of physical culture and sports in the country.

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ПОДГОТОВКА СТУДЕНТОВ В СФЕРЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗАХ РОССИИ: ОСНОВНЫЕ ЗАДАЧИ И ПРОГНОЗЫ НА БУДУЩЕЕ

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Аннотация

В статье анализируется физкультурно-спортивная деятельность студенческой молодежи на этапе профессиональной подготовки в вузе, где физическая культура приобретает профессиональное значение, поскольку способствует развитию молодого организма, формированию навыков здорового образа жизни, что в свою очередь приводит к повышению культуры физической активности и обеспечивает психофизическую подготовку к будущей профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: спорт, университет, страна, образование, студент.

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